

GEOSS content exploration

Technical Report

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Introduction and Scope

This report aims to support the work of the JRC.B6 (Digital Economy Unit), which provides scientific and technical services to the DG RTD for improving and evolving the GEOSS¹ (Global Earth Observation System of Systems) Platform. In the framework of this Administrative Agreement (called EOVALUE), a specific task deals with the analysis of the GEOSS users and data content.

The GEOSS platform is a global hub for Earth Observation (EO) data, representing an overarching infrastructure with the main task of easing discovery and access of data made available by different national and international organizations by means of heterogeneous publication systems.

GEOSS is managed and realized under the coordination of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO)², an intergovernmental initiative comprising more than 100 national governments and in excess of 100 Participating Organizations aiming to benefit different societal benefit areas by means of Earth Observations.

In 2017, an analysis of GEOSS data content and its users was done by JRC.B6 [1]. The present work aims to update such an analysis, in a consistent way, and understand the main changes occurred in the last few years.

¹ <https://earthobservations.org/geoss.php>

² <https://www.earthobservations.org/index.php>

Methodology

Analysis model

Information sources

The present analysis builds upon **two main information sources**, provided by the GEOSS Platform managers, as shown in Figure 1:

- 1) **The description of the datasets (i.e., the metadata) managed by the GEOSS Platform:** GEOSS datasets are contributed by the GEOSS data Providers. Each data Provider contributes information on shared georeferenced datasets (both in situ and remote observations) to the GEOSS Platform via heterogeneous Internet services.
- 2) **The description of the discovery requests finalized by the GEOSS Platform:** both humans (i.e., users) and machines (i.e., clients) submit discovery and access requests (i.e., queries) against the GEOSS Platform data content. Users interact with the platform through the GEOSS Portal³; while clients make use of heterogeneous Internet services.

Figure 1 The two information sources that have been used in this analysis, along with their contributors.

The two information sources are managed by a couple of DBMS. The database contents were analyzed to generate insights on **what GEOSS data Providers share** and **what GEOSS users/clients request**, respectively.

Dataset description analyzed

Dataset is the fundamental resource type shared through the GEOSS Platform: it can be defined as an **identifiable collection of data**⁴ representing an observation of the Earth (e.g., in-situ or remote observation), or a model output (e.g., a forecast).

As depicted in Figure 2, a GEOSS platform dataset is composed of:

³ <https://www.geoportal.org/>

⁴ ISO/TC211 (19115:2003)

- **Content** (the collected data), containing the values of the observation or forecast, encoded in different ways depending on the data Provider (e.g., binary, XML, CSV, etc.). The content analysis was left out, for the scope of this study,
- **Metadata**, a description of the dataset, composed of different metadata elements (i.e., discrete units of metadata, each documenting a specific aspect of the dataset). Presently, the GEOSS Platform provides several different metadata elements (in keeping with the ISO 19115 model); for the purpose of this study, only a subset of significant elements was analyzed. The examination focused on the following metadata elements:
 - [Mandatory] **Dataset provider** identifies the GEOSS dataset Provider, i.e., the organization that is responsible for the dataset sharing in GEOSS and for the metadata generation, publication, and maintenance.
 - [Optional] **Dataset cited organization** identifies an organization that is contributing to the dataset, with different roles (i.e., originator, publisher, contributor, ...).
 - [Optional] **Dataset spatial extent** identifies the geographic area covered by the dataset “content” (i.e., the spatial geometry defining the data geographic position and shape).
 - [Optional] **Dataset temporal extent** identifies the time period covered by the dataset “content” (i.e., the temporal geometry defining the data temporal occurrence and duration).
 - [Optional] **Dataset keyword**: identifies the commonly used word(s), formalized word(s), or phrase(s) used to describe the dataset.
 - [Optional] **Dataset keyword thesaurus** identifies the authorized source of keywords used.
 - [Optional] **Dataset title**: defines the name by which the dataset is known.
 - [Optional] **Dataset abstract**: defines a brief narrative summary of the dataset content.

All the metadata elements are optional except for the dataset *provider* element that is automatically generated by the DAB⁵.

⁵ <http://www.geodab.net>

Figure 2 GEOSS dataset main components and main metadata elements analyzed

Metadata analysis approach

The described metadata elements generate a multidimensional cube (i.e., information hypercube) where the subject is the collection of GEOSS datasets, and the metadata elements are the dimension of the hypercube --i.e., features. The cube is an information construct that is ready to be further explored by means of analytical tools, to address analysis demands.

Four general questions were considered as the basis for the discussed analysis: the classic “**What? Where? When? Who?**” questions. Each of these questions are addressed by a set of specific analysis operations on the multidimensional cube --e.g., slicing, drilling down, rolling up, pivoting, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Exploration of the generated metadata elements cube to investigate the analysis questions

For example, to address the question: “which organization contributed more datasets during 2020?”, it is possible: (a) first, to slice the data cube on the “Dataset temporal dimension” to select the datasets shared in 2020, then, (b) to completely roll up all the dimensions except the “Dataset source” dimension, to finally (3) produce a histogram chart having on the X axis the different “Dataset sources” and on the Y axis the count of the datasets shared by each source, in 2020.

GEOSS discovery requests

Discovery requests are performed by users and clients (i.e., Machine-to-Machine) to search GEOSS datasets matching a set of specific clauses –i.e., the query constraints. As depicted in Figure 4, a GEOSS discovery request is composed of:

- **Query content**, constituted by a set of query constraints (i.e., dataset metadata elements) and their occurrence values.
- **Query metadata**, a set of metadata elements that describe the query itself (e.g., the query timestamp and query originator IP address).

Figure 4 Components of GEOSS discovery query requests

The discovery requests analysis considered both the content and the metadata elements. The content investigation dealt with the following dataset metadata elements:

- **Dataset spatial extent**: geographic area (bounding box) specified in the query to restrict the result set to those datasets having spatial extent within it
- **Dataset temporal extent**: time period specified in the query to restrict the result set to those datasets having temporal extent within it

- **Dataset keyword:** search word or phrase specified in the query to restrict the result set to those datasets having a matching keyword

The query metadata analysis, on the other hand, focused on the following metadata elements:

- **Query date stamp:** the query timestamp indicating the precise time instant of query submission
- **Query originator IP address:** numerical label identifying the client originator of the query. This is extracted from the X-Forwarded-for HTTP header. Unfortunately, this important metadata element is available in the request logs only in requests made after 2018
- **Query originator country** (calculated): the country of the client originator of the query. This element has been calculated from the IP address through the *whos* Linux utility.
- **Query originator organization name** (calculated): the organization of the client originator of the query. This element has been calculated from the IP address through the *whos* Linux utility.
- **Days of use** (or **number of visits**, calculated): this metadata element is calculated starting from the originating IP address and the query date stamps and represents the number of days when the same originator client was active. As an example, if a user has made five requests to the GEOSS portal during day one and one request during day two, 2 days of use are counted for this user.
- **Query relative time:** the difference between the time of submission of the user request and the temporal extent requested by the user (e.g., “yesterday”, “the last five years”, etc.)

As for the dataset investigation, these elements generate a multidimensional information cube, where the subject is a discovery request, and its metadata elements are the dimensions –i.e., the features.

Four general questions were considered as the basis for the discussed analysis: the classic “**What? Where? When? Who?**” questions. Each of these questions are addressed by a set of specific analysis operations on the multidimensional cube --e.g., slicing, drilling down, rolling up, pivoting.

As well as for the dataset case the same four general questions “**What? Where? When? Who?**” were considered as the baseline for the analysis of discovery requests. Each of these questions are again addressed by a set of specific analysis operations on the multidimensional cube --e.g., slicing, drilling down, rolling up, pivoting.

Starting from the two types of information available, this analysis aims at understanding both the current content of the metadata available through GEOSS, and the most popular requests by the users, as far as the present GEOSS platform services. The next section details the actual process followed to extract the results, while the actual results and their interpretation is next available in two separate sections: one dedicated to GEOSS datasets and the other to GEOSS discovery requests.

Data management

Figure 5 shows the process applied during the analysis to answer the general questions that are the object of this study and produce the metrics and the diagrams which are presented in the next sections.

The GEOSS Platform build on a brokering middleware, called GEO DAB (Discovery and Access Broker) [2], which harvest, aggregate, and harmonize the dataset metadata contributed by the GEOSS data Providers.

Figure 5 The data sources management process applied for the analysis.

The GEO-DAB periodically harvests the Internet services, published by the GEOSS data Provider, to gather the metadata records describing shared datasets and consolidate them into the dataset DB, as XML documents based on the ISO 19115 standard. While the GEOSS discovery requests, managed by the DAB, are logged to another DB, as JSON records.

The applied procedure follows a general pattern originated from the data warehouse context, which is known as **Extract, Transform and Load (ETL)**. The general idea is to load the information to be analyzed (after validating it) into a system specifically designed to explore multidimensional information. The individual processing steps included in this analysis are detailed in the following paragraphs. Finally, the visualization step makes use of a specific tool to automatically realize plots and maps.

Extract

The information present in the relevant data sources is extracted from the original systems that are holding it for their specific purposes (i.e., from the **DAB metadata database** holding metadata records to enable GEOSS users to query them, and from the **request database**, holding request logs for logging purposes) and is externally consolidated as XML files and JSON files, in order to be further processed for the analysis purposes. In particular:

- Custom Java code (using aws S3 API) and the `m1cp` tool has been used to extract XML metadata documents from an aws S3 backup of the metadata database (based on MarkLogic DB) to the local file system.
- Custom Java code (using aws S3 API) has been used to extract JSON request documents from an aws S3 request backup to the local file system (for requests made before to May 2019)
- Custom Java code (using aws OpenSearch API) has been used to extract JSON request documents from an aws OpenSearch service to the local file system (for requests made after May 2019)

Transform

Starting from the XML metadata documents and the JSON requests, the transform process aims at producing JSONL files that are ready to be loaded in the data analysis service. The transform process involves:

- **Mapping** of metadata elements from the original metadata model to the target one. This step is needed to create records in a syntactic form that is supported by the data analysis service, so that they can be easily loaded.
- **Validation** of metadata elements (with failed validation resulting in ignoring the element, the complete record or marking it as invalid). This step can involve mapping in order to create records with values as expected by the data analysis service (**cleaning**), as well as remove records that don't contribute to the analysis content (e.g., invalid requests).
- **Augmentation** of metadata elements (joining specific metadata elements with additional content from external sources). This step is needed to augment the information content held by the original value (e.g., adding the country information from an IP address).

For the **GEOSS metadata documents**, the applied transformation tasks include:

- **Syntactical mapping** from XML elements to JSON elements.
- Mapping of **temporal positions** (applied to the fields “normalized_time_start”, “normalized_time_end”, “resourceTimeStamp”, “revisionDate”, “creationDate”, “publicationDate”, “dateStamp”). Example given:
 - “now” indeterminate position was mapped to current ISO8601 date time

- “Not complete” ISO8601 positions were completed, and time zone set to UTC (e.g. 2020 mapped to 2020-01-01T00:00:00.000Z)
- Validation of **temporal positions** with respect to “complete” ISO8601 standard. Temporal positions failing to validate against the time pattern "yyyy-MM-dd'T'HH:mm:ss.SSSZ" resulted in being ignored.
- Validation of spatial extent **bounding box** element: constraints on bounding box values have been considered (i.e. $-90 \leq \text{south} \leq \text{north} \leq 90$; $-180 \leq \text{east} \leq 180$; $-180 \leq \text{west} \leq 180$). Note: bounding boxes having east coordinate value less than west coordinate values are to be intended as crossing the antimeridian. Moreover, global bounding boxes (e.g., -180, -90, 180, 90) have been removed, as a search on all the globe doesn't add information with respect to the absence of bounding box constraints.
- Mapping of **bounding box** elements to geo shapes (required by the analysis service). Example geo shape: POLYGON ((-11.5 35.3, -11.5 81.4, 43.2 81.4, 43.2 35.3, -11.5 35.3))
- Mapping (cleansing) of **organization names**, including trimming of spaces and non-alphanumeric characters, removal of institution branches, malformed names, personal names, (German) town names, expansion of abbreviations, similarity pairing through Levenshtein distance and subsequent harmonization.

For the **GEOSS requests**, the applied transformation tasks include:

- **Syntactical update mapping** from outdated JSON model to updated JSON model (for requests before May 2019, recovered from backup).
- Mapping and validation of **temporal positions** (applied to the fields CHRONOMETER_TIME_STAMP, DISCOVERY_MESSAGE_tmpExtentBegin, DISCOVERY_MESSAGE_tmpExtentEnd), as described above.
- Validation of **bounding boxes**, as described above.
- Mapping of **bounding boxes** to geo shapes, as described above.
- Augmentation of **originating ip address**. Starting from the ip address documented in the field WEB_REQUEST_x-forwarded-for two additional elements are generated: country and organization. These two elements are retrieved using a custom java routine making use of the linux “whois” utility (a client to the whois directory service). When present in the “whois” response, the country metadata element will hold the ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code (two letter country codes, such as “IT”, “US”, “DE”, ...), useful to visualize on a map the request country of origin.

For example, the “whois” directory service information, which is used to augment the original request content (not relevant metadata elements omitted), is the following:

```
~$ whois 149.139.19.86
country:          IT
org-name:         Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
% This query was served by the RIPE Database Query Service version 1.101 (BLAARKOP)
```

Load

The loading phase ingests the transformed data into the **ElasticSearch** data system capable of performing multidimensional analysis. The custom java code loaded the JSONL transformed files using the *ElasticSearch* Java library into two main indexes: geoss-requests and geoss-metadata. *ElasticSearch* has been exercised both in its community edition version (released as a docker image) and as a cloud managed service at <https://www.elastic.co/> (enabling additional features). Elasticsearch is an enterprise search engine based on the Lucene library providing a scalable, distributed, multitenant-capable full-text search engine with an HTTP web interface and schema-free JSON documents. It can be queried using REST or Java based API.

Visualize

The API made available by *ElasticSearch* service can be used by the powerful visualization tool **Kibana**. It is sufficient to configure it with the endpoint of the *ElasticSearch* service to connect to it (or use the cloud managed version at <https://www.elastic.co/>) and start utilizing its user-friendly GUI in order to:

- **Explore multidimensional data** present in *ElasticSearch*. Through this Kibana functionality it is possible to show the overall data histogram over a specific time period (e.g., last 3 years), shown aggregated on a desired sub period (e.g., daily). A portion of non-aggregated data is also listed, in order to browse the actual information content and select filters (e.g., selected metadata values that should/shouldn't be shown).
- Create **visualizations from the data** present in *ElasticSearch*. Custom visualizations can be created from different basic types (e.g., **plots, gauges, graphs, maps**). After choosing the visualization type (e.g., line plot) it is possible to add metrics based on different aggregations (e.g., count, mean, max, average, ...) for the Y-axis, and it's possible to choose between different aggregations including by date histogram, date range, custom filters and so on for the X-Axis. The visualizations can then be further customized, also directly tuning *ElasticSearch* JSON settings to tailor them to the desired result.

Custom algorithms have also been applied to produce the keyword clustering visualization (where clusterization has been achieved through Force Atlas and modality-based Circle pack).

Analysis results

GEOSS datasets analysis

“What” analysis

Which datasets are analyzed?

Before presenting the obtained results, it is necessary to frame the GEOSS infrastructure in terms of its actors, components, and related data information flow (as depicted in Figure 6).

The GEOSS infrastructure is a distributed system of systems, composed of the following main components and actors:

- **GEOSS (data) Providers and Catalog services:** they are the organizations responsible for sharing metadata records on the GEOSS platform through their catalog services.
- **GEOSS (data) End-users and the GEOSS Portal:** organizations and individuals that search and collect GEOSS metadata records through the GEOSS Portal or other tools.
- **GEOSS Applications and Developers:** organizations responsible for implementing end-user tools interacting with the GEOSS Platform.
- **GEO Discovery and Access Broker (GEO-DAB):** the middleware component in charge of enabling the data information flow from the data Provider services to the End users' tools and applications, by means of metadata mediation, harmonization, and profiling services.

Figure 6 GEOSS infrastructure main actors and components.

The data Provider catalog services can be differentiated into three groups, depending on the implemented functionalities and related interactions with the GEOSS platform:

- **Harvestable:** they enable the periodical collection of the entire set of data Provider metadata records by the GEO-DAB harvester components. These records are stored into the DAB metadata database to enable subsequent fast user queries.
- **Searchable:** they do not allow harvesting but enable online searches for finalizing the received end user's discovery requests. Therefore, the DAB forwards the user queries to these data Provider catalogs in order to get matching results.

As a result, the following two searchable sources are not considered by this study:

- ArcGIS Online ESRI,
- USGS Earthquake.
- **Mixed:** they have only a subset of metadata records which are harvestable (usually the ones representing collections) while the collection data components (i.e., Granules) are only searchable at user query time. For example, a data Provider has Satellite data collections harvestable, but the single scenes are available only through direct search and access

This study considered the harvestable part (e.g., the satellite collections) of these components, only. The mixed sources recognized are:

- GBIF (Free and Open Access to Biodiversity Data),
- NextGEOSS,
- Ocean Biogeographic Information System,
- Federated EO Gateway (FedEO) – CEOS,
- CEOS WGISS Integrated Catalog (CWIC),
- CEOS International Directory Network (IDN).

This study analyzed the metadata records of the DAB metadata DB, snapshot of July 2021. Searchable catalogs are not part of this analysis. A future study might investigate the feasibility of analyzing the searchable catalogs, as well. It is noteworthy that main issues are related to data policy aspects and not to technological ones.

More than 42 million records (exactly, 42,171,856) were analyzed; Figure 7 shows the progressive increase of the number of harvested metadata records (in blue) along with the progressive increase of the number of their data providers (in red). Noteworthy, the number of retrieved records is by far greater than the one counted in the 2017, which was equal to 1.8 million. This significant increment is due to a couple of reasons:

- A physiological increment of the datasets managed by the sources recognized in 2017. In particular, the EU Copernicus Open Access Hub has substantially expanded the number of shared datasets.
- A significant increase of data providers (an increment of about 30%) who share their datasets through harvestable data sources.
-

Figure 7 Progressive increase of the number of harvested metadata records (in blue) compared to the progressive increase of the number of data providers (in red)

What are the main metadata elements analyzed?

For each metadata record, the elements searched are: (dataset) “provider”, “title”, “spatial extent”, “temporal extent”, “originator”, “abstract”, “keywords”. Table 1 reports the percentages of their occurrences:

Table 1 Metadata elements percentage occurrences

Metadata element	Occurrence percentage	
Provider:	100% ¹ ¹ The dataset <i>Provider</i> metadata element is generated by the DAB, automatically	
Title:	98.65%	
Spatial extent:	98.08%	
	Rectangular area	78.20% of all the dataset records (32979392 records)
	Point	19.88% of the all the dataset records (8387522 records)
Temporal extent:	90.56%	
Cited Organization and role	89.18%	
	role = Originator	34.38% ² of all the dataset records ² The 58.71% of the records with no <i>Originator</i> element stem from: EU Copernicus Open Access Hub, CUAHSI HIS, China GEOSS, USGS Landsat 8, WIS GISC DWD, and IRIS sources
Keywords:	20.79% ³ ³ The 75.39% of the records with no <i>Keywords</i> element stem from: EU Copernicus Open Access Hub, USGS Landsat 8, China GEOSS, and IRIS sources	
Keyword thesaurus [conditional]	16.61% ⁴ ⁴ The 79.92% of records containing a <i>keyword</i> (i.e., the 20.79% of the total records) has utilized a thesaurus (or controlled vocabulary).	
Abstract:	8.33% ⁶ ⁶ The 83.31% of the records with no <i>Abstract</i> element stem from: EU Copernicus Open Access Hub, CUAHSI HIS, USGS Landsat 8, and China GEOSS sources	

Some metadata elements are well present, in particular: (dataset) *source*, *title*, *spatial* and *temporal extent*, and *cited organization*; while other elements (or sub-elements) are largely missing (i.e., *originator* and *keywords*); finally, the *abstract* element is commonly missing.

The case of EU Copernicus Open Access Hub metadata records

As an example of the encountered issues regarding metadata quality, this section provides further details regarding the EU Copernicus Open Access Hub data provider.

In this case the DAB makes use of the M2M OpenSearch based API (published at scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/search) to incrementally ingest newly available metadata records.

The following sections illustrate the experienced drawbacks.

Lack of important metadata elements from the API

The metadata elements typically used to describe each record in the API responses are: “title”, “link”, “icon”, “datatakesensingstart”, “ingestiondate”, “beginposition”, “endposition”, “orbitnumber”, “relativeorbitnumber”, “cloudcoverpercentage”, “filename”, “gmlfootprint”, “format”, “identifier”, “instrumentshortname”, “sensoroperationalmode”, “instrumentname”, “footprint”, “s2datatakeid”, “platformidentifier”, “orbitdirection”, “platformserialidentifier”, “processingbaseline”, “processinglevel”, “producttype”, “platformname”, “size”, “tileid”, “hv_order_tileid”, “uuid”, “level1cpdiidentifier”, “datastripidentifier” (although some records have as well additional elements or may not have some of them).

As it can be seen, **important metadata elements are missing from the M2M API, notably, keyword and cited organization elements are not present** (see Annex A for an actual example response obtained from the API).

Missing INSPIRE metadata document from the API and in general

A further investigation has focused on comparing results obtained from the M2M API against results obtained from the human oriented web portal available at: <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus>, in order to understand if the missing information is available, and just currently not present in the API.

Figure 8 shows the visualization of a metadata record obtained from the web portal. As it can be seen, in the “Inspector” panel a link to an “INSPIRE.xml” file is available. By opening the link an ISO 19139 based XML file drafted according INSPIRE metadata technical guidelines (and hence potentially very useful) can be downloaded. **It would be very useful to have this same link in the responses of the M2M API**, so that the harvesting mechanism could obtain the same information that a human user can get.

However, not all metadata records have a link to an “INSPIRE.xml” file available, even from the web portal: Figure 9 shows the visualization of a metadata record not having the “INSPIRE.xml” link available.

Figure 8 Metadata record S2B_MSIL1C_20171231T141039_N0206_R110_T20KPF_20171231T205205 from EU Copernicus Open Access Hub. An "INSPIRE.xml" document is often linked from the "Inspector" panel.

Figure 9 Metadata record S1A_EW_GRDM_1SDH_20220127T115111_20220127T115146_041646_04F44E_60F9 from EU Copernicus Open Access Hub. The "INSPIRE.xml" document is not available.

Metadata content effectiveness

A third problem has been identified by analyzing the content of the INSPIRE metadata document obtained in the previous step.

Although the document appears syntactically correct and contains many metadata elements required by the INSPIRE directive, most of them are placeholders, limiting the semantic effectiveness of the provided information. For example, some metadata elements along with their

values are extracted from an actual metadata document and reported here for reference (the full sample can be found in Annex A):

- Cited organization name: “**org_name**”
- Cited organization e-mail: “**org_name@org.ext**”
- Format name: “**unknown**”
- Lineage statement: “**missing**”

Finally, keywords are present here, although they appear quite general (“**Orthoimagery**”, “**Land Cover**”, “**Geographical names**”, “**data set series**”, “**processing**”). Probably the discovery of these records would be improved by adding some more specific keywords (e.g., “Sentinel”, “Copernicus”, “EU”).

Discussion and possible way forward

The very low percentage occurrences of three key elements represent a major gap in GEOSS metadata quality and discovery match. This shortcoming should be addressed by GEO to understand, engaging with the data Providers, the reasons of the drawback and act accordingly - on a case-by-case way. For example, to improve the metadata completeness, some actions are suggested in order to support the GEOSS data Providers:

- **Provide feedbacks** to the data Provider and help the organization improving the quality of shared metadata.
- (Where feasible) **Automatically extract the missing content from the other present metadata elements** (e.g., the *keyword* element could be generated from other fields, such as the *abstract* and the *title*).
- **Check whether there is an interoperability issue** between the data Provider catalog and the GEOSS Platform.

If GEO were able to help the major data sources (e.g., EU Copernicus Open Access Hub, CUAHSI HIS, USGS Landsat 8, CHINA GEOSS, IRIS, Healthsites.io, and WIS GISC DWD) in fixing their present metadata shortcomings, the occurrences of all the metadata elements would become greater than 90%.

However, it is also important not only to check the presence of metadata values, but also their semantic effectiveness.

Another and more general approach to improve the metadata quality (and hence query matching effectiveness) might be to make the analyzed elements mandatory and not optional -see for example the adoption of the GEOSS Data management⁶ and FAIR principles⁷. However, considering the analysis results, that policy would drastically reduce the number and type of shared datasets through the GEOSS Platform, presently.

⁶

https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/binaries/web/global/news/2018/gdpw3_desherbini_et_al_day1_plenary-1700.pdf

⁷ [FAIR Principles - GO FAIR \(go-fair.org\)](https://www.go-fair.org/)

What are the main thesauri used for keywords?

Thesauri are controlled vocabularies for keywords. The use of thesauri is recommended to define a precise meaning (e.g., shared semantics inside a given domain community) of the utilized keywords. The utilization of “well-known” keywords/names is often an alternative of using free text. The most used thesauri (or controlled vocabularies) are: **CUAHSI Controlled Vocabularies** (i.e. “Data Type CV”, “Value Type CV”, “Quality Control Levels CV”), **PANGAEA** Project List, **GEMET** – EU INSPIRE themes, **WMO codes** (i.e. “CategoryCode”, “DistributionScopeCode”, “Radiosondes”), **Synoptic hours conventions**, **UN Sustainable Development Goals Taxonomy**⁹, **Mapbender controlled vocabulary**¹⁰, Global Change Master Directory (**GCMD**) (i.e. “Science Keywords”, “Data Center Keywords”, “Instrument Keywords”), Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (**ANZSRC**).

Significantly, about the 80% of found keywords were introduced following a thesaurus or a controlled vocabulary (see Table 1). This is important to enable semantic interoperability and query results effectiveness.

“Who” analysis

What about the GEOSS Platform data community?

GEOSS data community is composed by all the organizations contributing to dataset sharing through the GEOSS Platform. These organization can play several different roles, including data observation, metadata definition, dataset online publication, etc.

There are two metadata elements that refer to these organizations, as depicted in Figure 12:

- *data Providers and*
- *cited Organizations*, distinguishing according to the role played in dataset sharing process. For the scope of this analysis, it was distinguished between:
 - *data Originator*
 - *any other role*

⁹ <http://metadata.un.org/sdg>

¹⁰ mapbender.2.registryld

Figure 12 GEOSS platform data community

Who are the cited organizations?

Different organizations may play a role for the implementation of the dataset sharing workflow – e.g., to acquire, describe, contribute, publish, etc. To understand how large this Community is, it was analyzed the content of all the metadata elements that document (i.e., cite) one or more organizations regardless their role. The analysis recognized about 18 thousand unique organizations (exactly 18,738 ones).

Figure 13 shows the extent of the resulting Community along with the top cited organizations and their contribution in percentage.

Figure 13 Cited organizations pie chart.

At least one organization is generally documented for each GEOSS dataset -see Table 1. This helps understanding who the GEOSS dataset stakeholders are. Satellite data Providers (i.e., European Commission, China GEOSS, USGS, and NASA GES DISC) are the top cited organizations.

While, about 10% of all datasets does not contain any reference to an organization. This should be fixed by GEO as one of the necessary actions to improve the GEOSS platform effectiveness.

The following section will investigate the extension of those cited organizations that play the significant role of data *originator*.

Who are the data originators?

The pie chart of Figure 14 shows the top organizations that origin the datasets shared by the GEOSS platform.

Figure 14 Top organizations originating the datasets contributed to the GEOSS platform

The total number of recognized different *originator* organizations is 13,895. However, some of them are different ways to name the same organization (e.g., “NASA/JPL”, “NASA-JPL”, “NASA JPL Jet Propulsion Laboratory”, “NASAJPL (NASA)”, “NASA/JPL > JPL National Space Administration”). Once cleaned, the total number of unique *originator* organizations is **7,906** – naturally, the same issue and cleansing task was also performed for the cited organization analysis.

The *originators* analysis shows that the actual GEOSS community providing datasets is by far larger (i.e., one order of magnitude) than the number of sources identified by the data *Provider* metadata element –i.e., 196 data *Provider* values.

As reported in Table 1 and depicted in Figure 14, the *originator* element is often missing (65.62% of all the datasets), somehow limiting the insights provided by the current analysis and letting us suppose that the GEOSS community providing data is likely larger. Remote sensing data originators are underrepresented. European Commission appears to be the major originator, due to the data shared by the Copernicus Open Access Hub.

To address the issue of utilizing non-unique organization names, it is suggested the use of organization yellow pages (e.g., GCMD) and advancing the DAB capabilities to implement names harmonization.

Who are the data Providers?

Data *providers* are different from cited organizations, although, there is a big overlap. GEOSS data *providers* can be different from the dataset content originators. They are in charge of the datasets publication and online sharing, for example through catalog, registry, proxy, and listing services. A valuable instance is represented by PANGAEA. These organizations are the ones directly targeted by the DAB. According to this study, **the DAB recognizes 196 different GEOSS data providers.**

The pie chart in Figure 15 shows the ten data *providers* that contribute the most records to the DAB metadata DB. They are:

1. The **European Commission**, as the major contributor, sharing the **67.57%** of the total datasets through the **Copernicus Open Access Hub**.
2. The Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science, Inc. (**CUAHSI**), contributing with the **7.98%** of the total shared datasets
3. **USGS**, contributing with the **7.34%** of the total datasets, through **Landsat 8** data hub
4. **China GEOSS**, contributing with the **6.66%** of the total datasets
5. The Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology (**IRIS**), contributing with the **3.43%** of the total datasets
6. **Healthsites.io**, contributing with the **2.32%** of the total datasets
7. **WIS GISC DWD**, contributing with the **2.09%** of the total datasets
8. National Institute for Space Research - Brazil (**INPE**), contributing with the **0.78%** of the total datasets
9. **PANGAEA**, contributing with the **0.72%** of the total datasets
10. The **United Nations**, contributing with the **0.41%** of the total datasets, through the United Nations **Sustainable Development Goals** (UN-SDG)

All the other data *providers* represent the **0.71%** of the total.

Figure 15 Extent and percentage of GEOSS platform data records by provider.

Notably, the Copernicus Open Access Hub publishes about the 60% of the datasets shared through the GEOSS Platform. Four of the top ten providers share (also) in-situ datasets – i.e., CUAHSI-HIS, IRIS, WIS-GISC-DWD, Healthsites.io. In keeping with the provider percentages and their expected dataset contributions, it is possible to estimate that GEOSS Platform in-situ data are between 20% and 30% of the total.

Some remarkable percentage differences can be explained because of diverse granularity level characterizing the dataset content being shared. For example, the considered satellite sources (e.g., Copernicus Open Access Hub, USGS Landsat 8, and China GEOSS) share records at the granularity level of single observed scene.

“When” analysis

What is the dataset temporal extension?

For those datasets having a documented **temporal extent**, the plot of Figure 16 shows their occurrences by time. Temporal extent is the temporal information attached to the dataset by the

data *Provider/Originator*; this metadata element represents the temporal period covered by the dataset (i.e., the observation). The plot is centered on the temporal period that represents the majority of GEOSS data (i.e., the last 20 years). It is useful to note the existence of a long tail of data that have been acquired in the past (including historical records recently digitized). The top ten sources are depicted in Figure 16.

Figure 16 GEOSS dataset occurrences by their monthly-aggregated temporal coverage. Sentinel datasets are represented in green color (the data explosion on the right side). Forecast data is too small to be easily appreciated in the diagram.

The analyzed temporal coverages show an exponential growth of observations, in the last few years. That agrees with the increased availability of both in-situ and (predominantly) remote sensing datasets. As already discussed, most of these observations stems from the Sentinel sensors, whose granules (i.e., single scenes) are harvested by the DAB, continuously.

Importantly, there is a very small amount of synthetic data covering the next future (e.g., climate model forecasts). These data provide a good example of knowledge sharing as the result of an analytics process.

“Where” analysis

Where is the dataset spatial extension?

Almost all the records are georeferenced (see Table 1), Figure 17 shows the heat map of the world areas, which are the most covered by the datasets accessible through the GEOSS Platform.

Figure 17 GEOSS records by spatial coverage

The most observed areas are Europe and the USA. GEOSS Platform provides datasets on the polar areas (i.e., Svalbard and the Antarctic region) too. In general, we can notice that inland areas are better covered than oceans.

Who is providing data over Europe?

As shown by Figure 18, the leading data Providers contributing data over the European hotspots are:

- Copernicus Open Access Hub (62%)
- CUAHSI-HIS (10.43%)
- Healthsites.io (8.42%)
- USGS Landsat 8 (4.23%)
- China GEOSS (3.93%)

Figure 18 Top data providers sharing datasets covering Europe and detail of Europe spatial coverage

As expected, the Copernicus Open Access Hub is the major contributor of datasets observing Europe. CUAHSI-HIS is also well represented, although this is an US data Provider mostly sharing data related to hydrological in-situ measurements. This stems from the fact that CUAHSI-HIS also share satellite data that has a global extent –such as NASA GLDAS.

Who is providing data over the USA?

As shown by Figure 19, the leading data *providers* contributing observations over US hotspot are:

- Copernicus Open Access Hub (39.51%)
- CUAHSI-HIS (25.05%)
- IRIS (17.73%)
- WIS GISD DWD (5.15%)
- USGS Landsat 8 (4.52%)

Figure 19 Top data providers sharing datasets covering USA and detail of USA spatial coverage

The Copernicus Open Access Hub is the major datasets contributor (i.e., Sentinel global extent) for USA, as well. The datasets percentage of CUAHSI-HIS is very increased and IRIS Community datasets appear as the third contribution. The last two data *providers* are based in US and share in-situ data, mostly.

GEOSS Platform utilization analysis

“Who” analysis

Who are the GEOSS platform users and/or clients?

As depicted by Figure 20, **only a relatively small portion of the requests (about half a million requests, representing the 5.56% of the total) is traceable to the discovery requests made by the users of the GEOSS portal (<https://www.geoportal.org/>)**. Most of the registered

traffic (about 9 billion requests, representing the 93.0% of the total) was originated from machine-to-machine interactions (i.e., clients).

Most clients are harvesters (i.e., **automatic software agents**) that periodically request to download the entire data content of the GEOSS platform (or a relevant subset of it), for various purposes (such as its analytics). The main source generating the harvesting traffic is traceable to KMA (i.e., WMO WIS GISC). The other organizations generating significant harvesting traffic (to a much lesser extent, however) are USGS EROS and DLR (LOD-GEOSS). The other machine-to-machine requests originate from other interaction types (e.g., retrieval of metadata details, access of discovered datasets, etc.).

Figure 20 Main GEOSS user and clients: clients harvesting the platform data content represents most of the traffic, followed by human users utilizing the GEOSS portal

The following sections will focus on the users (i.e., human) interactions with the GEOSS portal, trying to characterize who they are, what they search, and how they express their searches.

How many user discovery requests in the last few years?

The Figure 21 plot shows the histogram of the user query requests submitted, via the portal, in the last four years. The average number of human requests is about 190 per day.

Figure 21 Number of requests per year submitted to the GEOSS portal

Referring to Figure 21, there is a general decrease of the human requests, as from 2018, passing from about 78 thousand requests in 2017 to about (expected) 60 thousand requests in 2021. The factors that have likely caused the decrease of about 23% of requests in four years can be multiple, including: a minor visibility of the GEOSS platform in the recent GEO activities and events; the discontinuation of the GEOSS Data Providers workshops; the launch of the GEOSS Knowledge Hub initiative with the lack of information on interoperability with the GEOSS platform; the new interest of the GEO Flagships in using public cloud platforms that provide satellite data access.

How many visits in the last few years?

About 68 thousand visits (each visit collecting all the requests made by a user in the same day) have been logged by the GEOSS platform. These are started by around 56 thousand unique users. On average, a daily visit consisted of 3.84 requests –with a median of 2 requests.

A returning user can be defined as a user who already utilized the GEOSS portal in the past (i.e., already submitted a discovery request) and returned to the portal for a new request. This piece of information is important because provides hints about the user satisfaction. In the past few years, the users who returned at least one time to the GEOSS Platform, were about 11,800, representing the 20.87% of all the unique users recognized by this study.

Figure 22 and Figure 23, respectively, the variation of the number of returning visits and their percentage, over the last four years. The number and percentage have diminished in the last two years (i.e., 2020 and 2021). In addition, consistently with the decrease of the number of requests (see Figure 21), the total number of visits significantly dropped in 2021.

Figure 22 Count of the visits started by returning users (the blue areas at the bottom of the columns) over the last four years

Figure 23 Percentage of the returning users out of the total number of users

However, the statistics on the number of returning users must be taken with caution because it is based on the recognition of user IP, but this approach is not able to identify a returning user if he/she makes use of dynamic IP allocation. This is common for the case of users who went in smart working due to the COVID. A possible way to solve this issue might be the introduction of a mandatory login on the GEOSS Portal --for example by using single sign-on mechanism. On the other hand, single sign-on could discourage some potential users to utilize the GEOSS Portal. Perhaps, a valuable compromise would be to utilize users data by implementing anonymization techniques with the only scope of statistics production.

More generally, GEO should further investigate the trends about returning users and, more generally, the users experience with the portal. Likely, the cancellation of the GEOSS Data Provider workshops created a certain disaffection of some users limiting the collection of their feedbacks and needs.

Who are the most active GEOSS portal users?

Analyzing the GEOSS Platform logs, the most active users (i.e., users who made the greatest number of requests over the few last years) are:

1. DLR – Germany (7,129 requests)
2. UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) - Great Britain (5,560 requests)
3. Fastweb (*) - Italy (3,560 requests)

4. European Space Agency (ESA) (6,640 requests)
5. COLT Technology Services (*) - Great Britain (1,070 requests)
6. Brennercom Tirol GmbH (*) - Austria (919 requests)
7. Accademia Europea di Bolzano – Italy (883 requests)
8. University of Tartu - Estonia (806 requests)
9. University of Geneva – Switzerland (774 requests)
10. Chinese University of Hong Kong - Hong Kong (635 requests)
11. National Technical University of Athens – Greece (501 requests)

**Telecommunication organizations providing Internet services. It is not possible to trace the actual users who are responsible for these requests.*

Therefore, the main users of the GEOSS Platform belong to the academia and research domain. In addition, there is a consistent user activity which seems to lead back to private and commercial organizations --making use of internet services providers.

For the number of days of use, Figure 24 shows that the most “loyal” users (i.e., the users who utilized the GEOSS platform the greatest number of days, over the last four years) have changed in the last four years. Notably, the total number of utilization days significantly dropped from more than 700 to less than 200.

Figure 24 Days of platform use of the most loyal users over time

Aggregating the utilization days over the past four years, the most active users are:

- 12. ESA - Italy (505 days)
- 13. UKRI - Great Britain (437 days)

14. Fastweb (*) - Italy (160 days)
15. DLR - Germany (133 days)
16. COLT (*) - Great Britain (92 days)
17. Ooredoo (*) - Qatar (86 days)
18. Deutscher Wetterdienst - Germany (86 days)
19. Google LLC (*) – USA (84 days)
20. Accademia Europea di Bolzano - Italy (78 days)
21. World Meteorological Organization - Switzerland (57 days)
22. Campus SFR - France (47 days)
23. Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy – Germany (59 days)
24. JAMSTEC - Japan (39 days)
25. University of Tartu - Estonia (39 days)
26. IHE Delft - The Netherlands (37 days)

**Telecommunication organizations providing Internet services. It is not possible to trace the actual users who are responsible for these requests.*

Also in this case, **research and academia organizations have been the most loyal along with a consistent activity interfaced by internet services providers –i.e., presumably, these visits are generated by private and commercial users.**

In the case of Google LLC, it is not easy to understand if the originator has been the Google private company itself, or the requests that have been made by the users of its cloud services.

As already discussed, a mandatory login mechanism to the GEOSS portal would improve the understanding of who are the actual GEO users.

Utilization evolution

To better understand the utilization evolution in the last few years,

Table 2 compares the number of utilization days between 2018 and 2021, for the most active users. **It is possible to infer the following trends: (a) UK most active organizations seem to have stopped using the platform; (b) ISPs significantly increased their activity, likely due to the smart working effect; (c) new users appeared, probably for accessing in-situ datasets.**

Table 2 Variation of the number of utilization days from 2018 and 2021, for the most loyal users.

Organizations	2018	2021	Notes
ESA - Italy	213	16	A significant drop of utilization days
UKRI - Great Britain	209	9	One of the top users (in 2018) almost disappeared in 2021

Google LLC - USA	60	52	Stable activity from Google services
Fastweb (*) - Italy	16	77	A significant increment of ISP activity, likely due to the smart working
COLT (*) - Great Britain	87	0	Disappeared in three years
Ooredoo (*) - Qatar	86	0	Disappeared in three years
Accademia Europea di Bolzano - Italy	50	7	Significant decrease of activity
The World Bank Group - USA	54	3	Almost disappeared in three years
DLR - Germany	19	27	Slight increase of activity
Campus SFR - France	21	13	A slight decrease
Bundesamt fuer Kartographie und Geodaesie – Germany	14	14	Stable activity
Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency - Japan	27	0	Disappeared in three years
Joint Research Center - Italy	23	4	A decrease of activity
Australian Department of Defence	7	13	A slight increase of activity
INGV – Italy	0	19	A significant increase of activity, likely due to the in-situ data availability
IHE Delft - The Netherlands	2	14	An increase of activity
National Observatory of Athens - Greece	2	9	Stable
Orange Polska (*) - Poland	0	10	A significant increment of ISP activity, likely due to the smart working
KPN (*) - The Netherlands	0	10	A significant increment of ISP activity, likely due to the smart working
University of Geneva - Switzerland	23	13	A significant decrease of activity

**Telecommunication organizations providing Internet services. It is not possible to trace the actual users who are responsible for these requests*

From which countries visitors come?

Figure 25 illustrate the top countries, from where the user requests were made. They are ordered by count and depicted with increasing dark red colors. The first five top countries are Germany, USA, Italy, Albania, and China.

Summing up the contribute coming from all the 27 countries of the European Union, it is possible to see that GEOSS platform usage from EU region is predominant, as shown by the blue area in the chart of Figure 25, confirming the relevant role of EU in GEOSS.

Figure 25 Countries originating the greatest number of requests to the GEOSS Platform. EU countries are depicted in blue.

Which are the most used keywords?

This study analyzed the requests started by users and finalized by the GEOSS platform, from January 2016 to December 2021 to recognize the most utilized query clauses. The most searched keywords (i.e., the “keyword” clause of user queries) are:

“chlorophyll”, “water”, “sentinel”, “earthquake”, “temperature”, “WMS”, “pollution”, “soil”, “wind”, “precipitation”, “sulfur dioxide”, “river”, “Landsat”, “flood”, “climate”, “deforestation”, “sea state”.

The top ten keyword occurrences (expressed in relative percentages) are depicted in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Relative percentages of the most searched keywords by GEOSS users

The keywords used in searches are rather general, mostly indicating either a theme (e.g., *pollution*), a parameter (e.g. *temperature*), or a natural element (e.g. *water*) with the exception of satellite names (i.e. *Sentinel* and *Landsat*) that indicate an observation source --in this case, the GEOSS platform is used as a data hub for satellite datasets.

Notably, some of the top keywords are expected to characterize the datasets shared by some of the major harvested GEOSS data Providers: for example, “Sentinel” and Copernicus Open Access Hub; “water” and CUAHSI-HIS; “earthquake” and IRIS. While the most popular keyword “chlorophyll” matches the US NODC Collections (which is at the 15th place amongst the data Providers) but it should also characterizes many of the datasets managed by the GBIF provider, which cannot be harvested presently. This limitation should be addressed by GEO.

Keywords evolution in the last few years?

Figure 27 shows the occurrences variation of the five most searched keywords, in the last six years.

Figure 27 Most searched keywords, by GEOSS users, over time.

In general, it is possible to say that user interest has changed few times in the last years. Table 4 reports the most searched keywords per year:

Table 4 Top searched keywords in the last few years

Year	1 st keyword	2 nd keyword	3 rd keyword	4 th keyword	5 th keyword
2016	WMS	sulfur dioxide	precipitation	sulfur	land cover
2017	water	earthquake	sentinel	precipitation	river
2018	chlorophyll	earthquake	water	sentinel	soil
2019	chlorophyll	water	earthquake	solar energy	land degradation
2020	water	temperature	sentinel	soil	meteorology
2021	soil	water	sentinel	earthquake	temperature

The keywords “sentinel”, “water”, “earthquake”, and “soil” are always present, over the past six years.

Which years users are interested in?

Requests having a time clause represent the 4.54% (19602 requests) of the total discovery requests and they are distributed by year of submission as shown by Figure 28.

The decreasing trend of the last years confirm the previous analysis on general discovery requests.

Figure 28 Time requests by year of submission

Figure 29 shows the most searched temporal extents (for simplicity, aggregated by year) by the GEOSS platform user, in the last few years.

The most searched year was the 2017, a large majority of request were generated by users in the 2017 itself and the year after –i.e., the 2018. Likely, this is due to the publication on the platform of the Sentinel datasets.

More generally, GEOSS platform users are interested in the more recent observation – i.e., datasets observed in the same year of the request.

Figure 29 Most searched temporal extents (with a yearly resolution). The different colors indicate the year when the query was issued.

Which areas users are looking for?

Many discovery requests, made by users, have a bounding box constraint. Figure 30 shows the all-time areas that have been most searched by the GEOSS Platform users.

Figure 30 Most searched spatial extents

According to Figure 30, Europe, North Africa, and the Middle East are the most searched areas as from the setup of the GEOSS Platform.

However, users interest has significantly changed in the last few years widening the searched area from the European continent to large parts of the other ones, as depicted in Figure 31, Figure 32, Figure 33, Figure 34, Figure 35, and Figure 36.

Figure 31 Most searched spatial extents in 2016 --i.e., Europe

Figure 32 Most searched spatial extents in 2017 –i.e., Europe plus Africa, South Asia, Australia and Americas

Figure 33 Most searched spatial extents in 2018 --i.e., Europe, Africa, South Asia, and Australia

Figure 34 Most searched spatial extents in 2019 --i.e., Europe, Africa, and part of Asia

Figure 35 Most searched spatial extents in 2020 --i.e., Europe, Asia, and Africa

Figure 36 Most searched spatial extents in 2021 --i.e., Europe and North Africa

Filtering data by user countries, it is also possible to visualize what are the most searched areas depending on the country where these searches come from. The following sections discuss the areas searched by the GEOSS users coming from the top five countries as to the number of requests –i.e., USA, Germany, China, Albania, and Italy.

What are the most searched areas from USA users?

USA users requested data covering different regions of the world, mostly USA and Europe, as shown in Figure 37:

Figure 37 Geographic areas that are most searched by USA users

What are the most searched areas from the EU users?

As shown in Figure 38, the areas predominantly searched by EU users are Europe, Middle East, and North Africa.

Figure 38 Geographic areas that are most searched by EU users

What are the most searched areas from China users?

As shown in Figure 39, the most searched areas by the Chinese users are China and Europe.

Figure 39 Geographic areas that are most searched by China users

What are the most searched areas from Germany?

Figure 40 shows the most searched areas by the German users, i.e., localities around Germany and Europe:

Figure 40 Geographic areas that are most searched by Germany users

What are the most searched areas by users from Albania?

As shown in Figure 41, the most searched areas by Albanian users are Kosovo and Albania (in a smaller percentage):

Figure 41 Geographic areas that are most searched by Albania users

What are the most searched areas from Italy?

As shown in Figure 42, the most searched areas by the Italian users are around Italy and Europe:

Figure 42 Geographic areas that are most searched by Italy users

Not surprisingly, in general, the most searched area matches with the country from where the searches originated. However, in some cases other areas are of interest for social and/or economic reasons.

Conclusions and recommendations

This report analyzes the **datasets** shared by the GEOSS data Providers via the GEOSS Platform as well as the **discovery requests** submitted by the GEOSS Platform users.

Limits of this study and recognized gaps

The present study has three main drawbacks: (a) because only the harvestable catalogs, shared by the data providers, are registered in the DAB DB, we could analyze part of the entire GEOSS Platform datasets offer, only; (b) the discovery requests logged before 2018 did not include the originating IP address. This limited a fully comparison with the more recent discovery requests; (c) some of the major data Providers do not provide a set of common metadata elements to describe the shared datasets. This limits some dataset quality analysis.

Main findings

In the last few years, the GEOSS Platform was mainly used by clients for machine-to-machine interactions. Harvesting requests have been, by far, the most relevant (in terms of traffic) activity engaging the platform. These requests came from a small number of organizations –e.g WMO, USGS EROS, and DLR.

Despite a significant growth of published datasets (especially satellite ones), there is the acknowledgement of an important decrease of user (i.e. human) requests, both in terms of absolute value and platform utilization days.

Most active users have changed over the last few years: some UK organizations do not seem to be active anymore. Besides, new research and academia organizations have become users of the platform, likely due to their interest in in-situ observations. Although, the main users belong to academia and research domain, after 2020, a notable increase of ISP activity raised.

Most of the requests submitted to the GEOSS Platform are originated by users from EU, USA, and China, respectively.

Though the in-situ datasets requests seem to be more and more popular, still, the search for satellite time series imagery (i.e., Sentinel and Landsat) are the top ones, by far. In general, the analysis acknowledged that the in-situ datasets are between 20% and 30% of the total.

The overall metadata quality of the datasets registered in the DAB DB is low, because some major data Providers do not specify a set of recommended metadata elements to describe their shared data –e.g., “keywords”, “abstract”, and “originating organization”.

Discussion

It seems that the GEOSS Platform has been used, in the past years, as a metadata aggregator and harmonization middleware by other platforms and/or information systems, pushing a machine-to-machine interaction.

The possible causes of the user requests drop can be multiple and connected each other. However, few likely reasons seem to be: (a) the progressive disconnection of the GEOSS platform from its data Providers and Users –a couple of valuable examples are the discontinuation of the GEOSS data Providers (and Users) workshop and the lack of the platform dissemination and training at the most recent GEO and GEOSS events; (b) the publication of the long time series of satellite datasets on public (and commercial) clouds –e.g., AWS, Google EE, and Microsoft Azure; (c) the COVID effect, with the advent of smart working and a decisive push of computing virtualization; (d) the launch of the GEOSS Knowledge Hub (GKH) initiative without a clear message about its synergy and interoperability with the GEOSS Platform.

Presently, looking at the platform content and user requests, GEOSS is popular as a Sentinel data access platform.

The acknowledged low level of quality of dataset descriptions stems from the difficulties encountered by the data Providers in the implementation of the GEOSS data management and FAIR principles and guidelines. Likely, it significantly contributed to that the already cited disconnection, recently experienced, between GEOSS Community and the platform.

RecommendationsPossible recommendations are: (a) to re-establish a strong connection with the GEOSS Community, restarting the holding of regular GEOSS data Providers and Users workshops also to the aim of formally identifying gaps and requirements to be subsequently implemented by the GEOSS platform; (b) to differentiate the needs of platform clients versus users, responding with more and more specialized services; (c) to present, in a clear manner, an overall design where the GKH is part of and advances the GEOSS Platform; (d) to reinforce the role of the GEOSS Platform for in-situ data sharing; (e) to advance the GEOSS platform capabilities by adding computing scalability –relying on existing and distributed infrastructures.

It is recommended to engage the GEOSS Community with the aim of improving the present quality level of shared data –i.e. metadata elements to describe the datasets. As pointed out in the analysis three general actions could be performed together with each data provider to significantly improve the metadata quality:

- Provide feedback to the metadata authors
- Automatically produce missing metadata from available metadata (e.g., produce keywords from abstract)
- Identify possible interoperability issues between the data Provider catalog and the GEOSS platform

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Annex A: Copernicus Open Access Hub samples

Metadata record from M2M API

This example shows the metadata record obtained as a response from the Copernicus Open Access Hub OpenSearch API to the following request:

[https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/search?q=ingestiondate%3A%5B%202014-01-01T00:00:00Z%20T0%202018-01-01T00:00:00Z%5D%20AND%20\(filename%3AS1A *%20OR%20filename%3AS1B *%20OR%20filename%3AS2A *%20OR%20filename%3AS2B *%20OR%20filename%3AS3A *\)&rows=1&start=1](https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/search?q=ingestiondate%3A%5B%202014-01-01T00:00:00Z%20T0%202018-01-01T00:00:00Z%5D%20AND%20(filename%3AS1A *%20OR%20filename%3AS1B *%20OR%20filename%3AS2A *%20OR%20filename%3AS2B *%20OR%20filename%3AS3A *)&rows=1&start=1)

Response metadata record:

```
<entry>
  <title>S2B_MSIL1C_20171231T141039_N0206_R110_T20KPF_20171231T205205</title>
  <link
    href="https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/odata/v1/Products('4a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f')/$value"/>
  <link rel="alternative"
    href="https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/odata/v1/Products('4a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f')/" />
  <link rel="icon"
    href="https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/odata/v1/Products('4a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f')/Products('Quicklook')/$value"/>
  <id>4a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f</id>
  <summary>Date: 2017-12-31T14:10:39.027Z, Instrument: MSI, Satellite: Sentinel-2, Size: 51.27 MB</summary>
  <ondemand>>false</ondemand>
  <date name="datatakesensingstart">2017-12-31T14:10:39.027Z</date>
  <date name="ingestiondate">2017-12-31T23:59:52.728Z</date>
  <date name="beginposition">2017-12-31T14:10:39.027Z</date>
  <date name="endposition">2017-12-31T14:10:39.027Z</date>
  <int name="orbitnumber">4283</int>
  <int name="relativeorbitnumber">110</int>
  <double name="cloudcoverpercentage">65.905</double>
  <str
name="filename">S2B_MSIL1C_20171231T141039_N0206_R110_T20KPF_20171231T205205.SAFE</str
r>
  <str name="gmlfootprint">&lt;gml:Polygon
    srsName="http://www.opengis.net/gml/srs/epsg.xml#4326"
    xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml"&gt; &lt;gml:outerBoundaryIs&gt;
      &lt;gml:LinearRing&gt; &lt;gml:coordinates&gt;-18.1677298403753, -
61.15321400575774
-18.06594942797048, -61.128229281880586 -17.91798753592628, -61.09193613278399
-17.770040093650906, -61.055521746791136 -17.633790281244206, -
61.022463012934175
-18.16668895738219, -61.01663542419426
-18.1677298403753, -61.15321400575774&lt;/gml:coordinates&gt;
&lt;/gml:LinearRing&gt;
&lt;/gml:outerBoundaryIs&gt; &lt;/gml:Polygon&gt;</str>
```

```

    <str name="format">SAFE</str>
  <str
name="identifier">S2B_MSIL1C_20171231T141039_N0206_R110_T20KPF_20171231T205205</str>
    <str name="instrumentshortname">MSI</str>
    <str name="sensoroperationalmode">INS-NOBS</str>
    <str name="instrumentname">Multi-Spectral Instrument</str>
    <str name="footprint">POLYGON ((-61.15321400575774 -18.1677298403753,-
61.128229281880586
    -18.06594942797048,-61.09193613278399 -17.91798753592628,-61.055521746791136
    -17.770040093650906,-61.022463012934175 -17.633790281244206,-
61.01663542419426
    -18.16668895738219,-61.15321400575774 -18.1677298403753))</str>
    <str name="s2datatakeid">GS2B_20171231T141039_004283_N02.06</str>
    <str name="platformidentifier">2017-013A</str>
    <str name="orbitdirection">DESCENDING</str>
    <str name="platformserialidentifier">Sentinel-2B</str>
    <str name="processingbaseline">02.06</str>
    <str name="processinglevel">Level-1C</str>
    <str name="producttype">S2MSI1C</str>
    <str name="platformname">Sentinel-2</str>
    <str name="size">51.27 MB</str>
    <str name="tileid">20KPF</str>
    <str name="hv_order_tileid">KF20P</str>
    <str name="uuid">4a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f</str>
    <str name="level1cpdiidentifier"
    >S2B_OPER_MSI_L1C_TL_MTI_20171231T205205_A004283_T20KPF_N02.06</str>
    <str name="granuleidentifier"
    >S2B_OPER_MSI_L1C_TL_MTI_20171231T205205_A004283_T20KPF_N02.06</str>
    <str name="datastripidentifier"
    >S2B_OPER_MSI_L1C_DS_MTI_20171231T205205_S20171231T141344_N02.06</str>
  </entry>
</feed>

```

INSPIRE metadata document

The following metadata document has been retrieved from the link made available from the Copernicus Open Access Hub web portal:

[https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/odata/v1/Products\(%274a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f%27\)/Nodes\(%27S2B_MSIL1C_20171231T141039_N0206_R110_T20KPF_20171231T205205.SAFE%27\)/Nodes\(%27INSPIRE.xml%27\)/\\$value](https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/odata/v1/Products(%274a49627c-3c2d-4596-9caa-70a4910edf7f%27)/Nodes(%27S2B_MSIL1C_20171231T141039_N0206_R110_T20KPF_20171231T205205.SAFE%27)/Nodes(%27INSPIRE.xml%27)/$value)

Metadata document:

```

<gmd:MD_Metadata xmlns:gco="http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gco"
xmlns:gmd="http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd" xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml"
xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd
http://schemas.opengis.net/iso/19139/20060504/gmd/gmd.xsd">
  <gmd:fileIdentifier>
    <gco:CharacterString>publisher</gco:CharacterString>

```

```

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erSetCode" codeListValue="MD_CharacterSetCode_utf8"
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codeListValue="dataset">dataset</gmd:MD_ScopeCode>
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        </gmd:contactInfo>
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```

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(EU) No 1089/2010 of 23 November 2010 implementing Directive 2007/2/EC of the
European Parliament and of the Council as regards interoperability of spatial data
sets and services</gco:CharacterString>
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